

1 Vaccine Biology and Strategies: Why do we wait ten years to vaccinate our children against
2 papillomavirus?

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7 Prevailing thought is likely that sexual contacts do not begin until adolescence. Cross neutralizing potential
8 against skin-endemic beta genus papillomaviruses conferred to varying degrees based on L1 type at
9 vaccination is not yet understood and likely poor at best. Papillomavirus vaccinations require broader
10 protection (higher valency) and are likely to be most effective when provided at the earliest age at which
11 mucosal immunity can be effectively established.

12 Citations

- 13 1. Harper, D.M. and Paavonen, J., 2008. Age for HPV vaccination. *Vaccine*, 26, pp.A7-A11.
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